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The Role of Media in European Anti-Gender Politics

Research Findings
from the RESIST Project

English

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Deutsch

‘Anti-gender’ politics are distorting the public debate about gender equality and LGBTIQ+ people in Europe.

RESIST is an EU-funded research consortium comprising 10 research institutions. The project examined the dynamics of organised opposition, often taking the form of coordinated attacks, against recent advances in gender equality, reproductive rights, and the rights and representation of LGBTIQ+ people.

RESIST also analysed the social and political impacts of these mobilisations, including their effects on targeted communities and on democratic societies more broadly.

This resource draws on two RESIST substudies:

- I A media study that analysed data from over 2000 articles from 87 media outlets in the UK, Switzerland, Poland, and Hungary.
- II A study focusing on those targeted by ‘anti-gender’ politics, for which we collated over 250 interviews with people targeted by organised opposition to gender and sexual equality and rights, from eight countries, and with people living in exile because of persecution, relentless controversies and attacks. Interviewees included activists, authors, journalists, researchers, counsellors, educators, and politicians. Additionally, we interviewed 30 civil society experts who work on gender and LGBTIQ+ equality.

We found that media, across the political spectrum, play a significant role in ‘anti-gender’ politics in our research contexts. Sensationalist and hostile reporting has become a key focus of right-wing media, but it is not exclusive to them. Diverse media sources in an environment defined by competition for attention amplify these controversies and narratives. These factors result in LGBTIQ+ minorities, particularly trans people, being highly visible yet largely voiceless in hostile debates.

Our media study demonstrated that there is a constant media platform for ‘anti-gender’ politics, facilitating actors who oppose gender and sexual equalities to shape public attention and mobilise supporters for reactionary political agendas. At the same time, feminist and LGBTIQ+ civil society organisations lack access to news coverage and to shaping news framing.

This resource for journalists highlights how media generate and amplify ‘anti-gender’ controversies, and what effect this has on civil society and democracy.

What are ‘Anti-Gender’ Politics?

- I **We use the term ‘anti-gender’ politics to describe organised opposition, often in the form of attack, to recent social progress in gender equality, reproductive rights, and the rights and representation of LGBTIQ+ people. In RESIST, we do not limit this analysis to the far right; instead, we examine ‘anti-gender’ politics across the political spectrum.**
- II **This broader perspective is essential as gendered and sexual inequalities continue to shape our societies. Our research shows that ‘anti-gender’ politics take root in these existing inequalities. Coordinated opposition to women’s and LGBTIQ+ rights, along with hostile debates aimed at feminists and queer people, reinforces existing patterns of discrimination.**

- I In recent decades, research in the social sciences and humanities has fundamentally reshaped how we understand gender inequality. Many studies have shown that gender norms are socially and culturally constructed, rather than fixed by nature. The concept of gender has therefore been used to question rigid ideas about the gender binary, gender identity, heterosexuality as the 'natural' foundation of society, and traditional expectations of women's and men's roles and behaviour.
- II Building on these insights, many current policies aimed at equality and diversity recognise gender inequality as a social issue that can be changed. In response, different political actors have turned the term 'gender' into a political target.
- III The far right and some conservative and religious actors campaign against the idea of gender, arguing that they are protecting a 'natural order' of society with fixed roles for men and women. In addition, some feminists who describe themselves as 'gender-critical' also defend the idea of biological sex over gender, which they believe should form the basis for feminism. However, this view has been criticised by many feminists as being exclusionary of both trans women and non-binary people.
- IV In RESIST, we distance ourselves from this political targeting of gender and therefore single quote 'anti-gender' to indicate that it is used critically.

Campaigning Media

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In the RESIST studies, we found that reactionary media outlets actively campaign on ‘anti-gender’ issues. The specific issues vary by country but commonly include: trans rights, LGBTQ+ rights, abortion, gender quotas, sex education, feminist or LGBTQ+ inclusive children’s books or films, and progressive (LGBTIQ+ inclusive) Christian congregations.

Campaigning media outlets produce large volumes of ‘anti-gender’ content, including both misinformation and disinformation, and are openly hostile towards feminists and LGBTQ+ people. They use demeaning or inflammatory language against political opponents and sometimes engage in smear campaigns.

Cyphers such as ‘gender ideology’ or ‘woke’ are widely used in right-wing media to dismiss feminist and LGBTQ+ issues. A cypher is a term that is strategically chosen in political debates to signal threats or enemies through constant repetition. Conspiracies and moral panics are generated around equality legislation, reproductive rights, education, or the mere existence of minorities, portraying them as threats to the family, society, or the nation. These narratives can be reproduced in news, editorials, and opinion pieces alike.

Campaigning media often amplify international figures known for anti-feminist, anti-LGBTIQ+, or anti-trans positions. Politicians, intellectuals, and activists who hold such positions are frequently platformed through prominent news coverage and commentary.

Coverage in these outlets tends to source and quote political actors and organised campaign networks, including think tanks, activist groups, and social media entrepreneurs. This disproportionate inclusion allows ‘anti-gender’ messages to be amplified across multiple platforms simultaneously. Some reactionary activist groups present themselves as ordinary citizens or parents, but they are often highly organised campaigns with clear political agendas, funding, and established strategies and networks.

Right-wing media benefit from cross-platform sharing that creates content saturation and reinforces confirmation bias. They aim to provoke engagement, comments, shares, and visibility on social media.

‘Anti-gender’ content is not only the result of campaigning journalism. It is also the effect of reactionary media outlets recycling such content as a commercial strategy, capitalising on its popularity and sensational appeal. Because news is increasingly accessed digitally, attention strategies for digital platforms often prioritise ‘rage bait’ and other kinds of manufactured controversies in the competition for attention.

Research Spotlight. Constructing Controversy

Trans Politics in the UK Media

- I Our analysis of three UK newspapers (The Guardian, The Telegraph, and The Scotsman) shows that coverage of trans issues has become a central part of right-wing media ‘culture wars’. In this context, trans people are often directly targeted, with debates about gender and sexuality being presented as part of a larger social or political conspiracy.
- II This pattern is especially visible in The Telegraph, which frequently publishes critical and hostile stories about trans people. Our findings suggest that this is part of a wider right-wing media network, including outlets like GB News and groups such as the Free Speech Union, which continuously share and repeat each other’s content.
- III By doing so, these actors flood media spaces with anti-trans messages, making them seem more widespread and thereby more credible. In this environment, sensational and provocative stories get more attention and more clicks. This isn’t just about ideology; it’s also about profit. Outlets like GB News use controversy to attract viewers and revenue, regularly flouting regulatory standards to do so.
- IV These media platforms also present themselves as ‘defenders of free speech’, claiming that support for trans rights limits expression. This argument feeds into a broader story that paints ‘gender ideology’ as censorship, while portraying anti-trans coverage as courageous and truth-telling.

How News Coverage Amplify 'Anti-Gender' Messages

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Our studies show that broadsheet media is a central arena for 'anti-gender' politics; it can amplify and reproduce related controversies. Interviewees have stressed that these positions are advanced and normalised in this way.

Key mechanisms of amplification include:

- I Sources with controversial views on feminist and LGBTIQ+ issues are quoted without transparent declaration of their political background and ties.
- II Cyphers such as 'gender ideology' or 'woke', originating from reactionary actors, are repeated by journalists without quotation marks, context, or definition. This reproduces reactionary terminology and embeds it in mainstream debates.
- III Media adopt the dramatic frames of 'anti-gender' actors. This includes spreading misinformation, discrediting gender studies scholars or feminist and LGBTIQ+ civil society organisations, and framing equality demands as crises threatening women's rights, children, parental rights, society, or democracy. For example, advocacy by feminist and queer groups is sometimes framed as a threat to freedom of speech or democratic institutions.
- IV Media reporting often platforms reactionary figures as one side in a substantial debate, rather than critically examining the ideas they promote. This allows hateful positions to spread unchallenged.

- V **Media outlets amplify disputes through commentaries and opinion pieces from authors with controversial views on feminist and LGBTQ+ issues.**
- VI **Media do not give substantive representation to feminist and LGBTQ+ voices from civil society. Organisations, particularly trans groups, are frequently spoken about rather than given a platform. Anti-trans or so-called 'gender critical' voices receive disproportionate access to media, forcing civil society to react to controversies rather than shape debates. Across contexts, our data shows that feminist and LGBTQ+ organisations face significant challenges in agenda-setting.**
- VII **Media adopt a 'middle ground' approach, presenting themselves as impartial while equating reactionary actors with feminist and LGBTQ+ civil society. This creates the misleading impression of equivalence and downplays the danger of reactionary politics.**

Disinformation Flow. From 'Anti-Gender' Narratives to Mainstream Normalisation

I Origin of 'anti-gender' actors

'ANTI-GENDER' ACTORS INVENT
AND CIRCULATE CYPHERS SUCH AS 'GENDER
IDEOLOGY' AND 'WOKE'.

THROUGH STRATEGIC FRAMING,
THEY PORTRAY EQUALITY AND INCLUSION AS
SOCIETAL THREATS.

II Media uptake in the amplification stage

CYPHERS ARE OFTEN REPEATED
WITHOUT SUFFICIENT CONTEXT OR CRITICAL
QUOTATION MARKS.

AS A RESULT, 'ANTI-GENDER' VOCABULARY
ENTERS MAINSTREAM DISCOURSE.

III Sensationalist framing

MEDIA OUTLETS USE DRAMATIC, CONFLICT-
ORIENTED NARRATIVES.

GENDER EQUALITY IS FRAMED AS A 'CRISIS'
OR A 'THREAT'.

IV Agenda distortion

COVERAGE SHIFTS THE FOCUS TO ACTORS RATHER THAN IDEAS.

MEDIA ATTENTION CENTERS ON 'ANTI-GENDER' PERSONALITIES INSTEAD OF ~~CRITICALLY EXAMINING THEIR IDEOLOGIES.~~

CONTROVERSIAL FIGURES GAIN VISIBILITY AND LEGITIMACY.

V Silencing and displacement

MARGINALISED FEMINIST AND QUEER VOICES, SUCH AS TRANS PEOPLE, ARE SPOKEN ABOUT RATHER THAN GIVEN SPACE TO SPEAK.

AT THE SAME TIME, 'ANTI-GENDER' VOICES DOMINATE AIRTIME.

VI False balance

MEDIA PRESENT 'BOTH SIDES' AS EQUALLY VALID.

THIS FRAMING EQUATES DISCRIMINATORY NARRATIVES WITH ~~HUMAN RIGHTS ADVOCACY.~~

Impact of 'Anti-Gender' Messages in the Media

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In recent years, transnational 'anti-gender' politics have fuelled growing hostility toward LGBTIQ+ people, particularly trans individuals, and have undermined feminist achievements, including the Istanbul Convention and reproductive rights.

Academic studies have highlighted the surge in negative media representations of trans people. Our research confirms that across multiple countries, media outlets not only amplify but also mainstream reactionary messages, targeting feminists, LGBTIQ+ people and especially targeting trans people.

Interviews with those targeted by 'anti-gender' politics, such as politicians, academics, authors, journalists, and activists, revealed that hostile media debates are a shared source of concern. Far-right media campaigns often single out individuals, creating a chilling effect that limits their participation in public debates. Many of our interviewees, including journalists, reported being personally targeted by campaigning media outlets, which resulted in being harassed and threatened.

The situation is particularly dramatic for trans people who are highly visible in public debates, yet are rarely allowed to speak for themselves. Media coverage often sensationalises their lives, reinforces harmful stereotypes, and amplifies moral panics. In mediated controversies, trans existence and rights are frequently framed as threats to women's rights or child development, justifying hostility towards trans people and opposition to their rights. This hostile focus on trans people stems from both contentious legislative debates and deliberate efforts by politicians and media to present transgender identities as urgent societal problems.

Hostile media reporting harms the health and well-being of feminists and LGBTIQ+ people, restricting their participation in public debate and reducing the diversity of voices in public discussions. The circulation of 'anti-gender' narratives in broadsheet media further undermines their trust in journalism. Meanwhile, the mediatisation of controversies limits civil society organisations' ability to secure funding, deliver services, conduct outreach, and organise safe public events.

Glossary

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Cancel culture

A term used to criticise or delegitimise forms of public debate, protest, and accountability practices. In reactionary discourse, ‘cancel culture’ is portrayed as a coercive or punitive approach to silencing dissenting voices, often linked to progressive social movements.

Gender Critical Feminism

A self-label for a branch of feminist thought that emphasises a biological understanding of sex. The term emerged to affirmatively describe a feminism that excludes trans people and to evade the negatively framed label Trans-Exclusionary Radical Feminist (TERF). ‘Gender-critical’ feminists have been contested for their alignment with reactionary actors and their narratives.

Gender ideology

A strategic, emotionally charged term deployed by ‘anti-gender’ actors to frame social issues as threats. As a ‘cypher’, its meaning shifts across contexts to serve different political agendas: in the UK, it often targets trans rights, while in Poland and Hungary, it challenges reproductive rights, LGBTIQ+ visibility, and comprehensive sexuality education. Its vagueness allows multiple issues to be conflated, portraying a broad and dangerous threat, and making the underlying claims harder to contest.

A flexible, emotionally charged term used by ‘anti-gender’ actors to portray certain social issues as harmful or inappropriate. Its meaning shifts across contexts: in Poland, it is directed against trans autonomy, feminist perspectives, LGBTIQ+ activism, sexual education, and women’s rights; in Switzerland, it is used to oppose comprehensive sexuality education and gender-affirming healthcare for trans youth.

TERF

(Trans-Exclusionary Radical Feminist)

A movement term for feminists who explicitly exclude trans women from women’s spaces and feminist advocacy. Often associated with ‘gender-critical’ feminism, TERFs oppose legal, social, and medical recognition of trans identities, framing sex-based rights as incompatible with gender identity inclusion. The term is widely used in academic and activist contexts to highlight exclusionary practices within feminist movements.

Woke

A widely recognised, emotionally charged term used to dismiss or undermine anti-racist, feminist, queer, and climate justice claims. In reactionary discourse, ‘woke’ is framed as an illiberal, top-down ideology imposed on society, portraying progressive social movements as a threat to ‘the people’.

Explore More RESIST Resources

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All RESIST resources are available on the [RESIST website](#) and [project repository](#), offering evidence, guidance, and interactive tools for journalists, policy-makers, and civil society.

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Explore
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Resources

For Civil Society. Strengthening Civil Society Against Anti-Gender Politics

A summary of our research findings on common strategies and tactics used by ‘anti-gender’ actors, the effects of ‘anti-gender’ politics on individuals, communities, and democracy, and the ways in which civil society resists and responds to these challenges.

RESIST/ANCE. Strategies for a Better World

An interactive, collaborative serious game for 2-3 players (or larger workshops) that helps participants explore how ‘anti-gender’ mobilisations operate, their real-world impacts, and strategies to resist them. RESIST/ANCE provides a safe space to learn, reflect, and act together. The game is available for free. For more information, visit the RESIST project website.

For Policy Makers. Policy Brief and Policy Recommendations

A summary of our findings highlighting the impact of ‘anti-gender’ politics, and concrete recommendations for policies and interventions that support inclusive and democratic responses across Europe.

Research Reports

Detailed reports presenting the project’s methodologies, case studies, and in-depth analysis of ‘anti-gender’ politics across Europe.

Solidarity and Struggle. Resisting Anti-Gender Politics

A free self-paced online course aimed at non-specialist, general audience learners. Using interactive activities, it conveys the findings of the RESIST Project and other research about ‘anti-gender’ mobilisations.

For all materials and downloads, visit the **RESIST website and project repository.**

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Project Deliverable D4.1:

Tools for stakeholders including policy recommendations. Work Package 4 - Re-invigorating Feminist Theories.

Outputs repository

zenodo.org/communities/resistproject

Project website

theresistproject.eu

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